

NPS Better predict online classroom

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Abstract

By 2020, Thailand and other countries around the world have experienced severe COVID-19 in almost every corner of the world, China, Japan or even the United States. Was also greatly affected as a result of this impact on teaching and learning management for students, which was originally a Face-to-face system, the teaching model has been changed to be an online classroom system such as Google classroom Zoom meeting Hangout skype etc. In order to evaluate the online teaching and learning model in the Thai education system therefore created a satisfaction evaluation form of 89 students in bachelor degree with online teaching. By using the Net Promoter Score (NPS) business recommendation method. The student group like a customers, by dividing the group of respondents according to a score of 0 to 10. Student groups were satisfied with traditional teaching and suggesting methods. This group is in the form of Promoter, representing 13.6 percent. For the group of students who are not satisfied with the online teaching style and do not recommend further This group is in the form of Detractor, representing minus 6.7 percent and the assessment of satisfied for traditional teaching score 75 percent, which is considered a very satisfactory level.

Keywords: Active Learning; Engineering Education; Conference Information; Project Approaches.

1 Introduction

Since the beginning of 2020, Thailand and other countries around COVID-19 have changed the universities in Thailand to use online education. In this case, the objective is to assess the current trend of online teaching styles at the bachelor degree. By evaluating the learning of students which may cause some student not have computer, internet connection and more problems, etc. Assessment of online teaching in this critical situation, (Rompho, 2020) studied the evaluation in the form of Net Promoter Score (NPS) as well as customers doing small online for evaluating transactions using the Net Promoter method before you will receive one client survey request: levels 0 to 10, where 0 = none and 10 = sure. Please rate your willingness. To recommend us to others (Nicholas & Kordupleski, 2018) assessments are important both in designing online courses and as a mechanism for learning quality assurance. In this article, the issues that assess online teaching and learning are considered. There are different incentives for evaluation and strategies for meeting these needs. The UK government has a broad impact on tertiary education. Part of this effect has increased the importance of evaluation.

However, the evaluation drive is not matched by support and training for workers who should perform these processes (Oliver, 2000)

Peters (1998) Identify many differences between distance learning and traditional education. These include: Teaching 'writing' is the opposite of teaching 'speaking'. Learning 'reading' focuses on 'listening' learning.

The results from the use of technical and electronic media, including three different teaching structures, were created, which are teaching styles.

The social status of distance students is very different in terms of the decisions of students at traditional universities. Specific conditions of institutions and institutions are necessary for the development of controls and evaluations.

The latest emerging trends in E-learning assessments are reviewed and explored to address the latest topics and participation in the age of distance education. Which has been rigorously examined in identifying and

detailed research projects, frameworks and modern techniques for evaluating E-learning using methods such as Blockchain, Gamification, Process Mining and MOOC (Lara, Aljawarneh, & Pamplona, 2019)

The online teaching point of view that many systems use is especially important for closed online conversations, as is learning by letter. It can be seen that this is very useful for assessors. For effective teaching and learning during this critical time, the researchers used NPS evaluation methods. To assess student satisfaction in online learning The format of the question is short, concise and easy to understand. Makes it able to evaluate the teaching model effectively

The 'Teaching and Assessment Policy' The purpose of this policy is to ensure that every teaching and evaluation program passes, especially to at-risk sub-groups. There are 3 ways to evaluate teaching (Figure 1.) (Curriculum, Teaching and Assessment, 2020)

Figure 1. Curriculum, teaching and assessment linked. (Curriculum, Teaching and Assessment, 2020)

From Figure 1. Explain that the teaching and evaluation courses are inseparably linked It can be seen that when all three are in the same line, they are the most effective and highest quality learning effective for all students, regardless of the starting point. On the other hand, this should translate to all students to make good progress and achieve the best academic results. Because it gives them the best opportunity to learn.

This paper assesses the effective and problem of online learning. Based on study group satisfaction of bachelor degree 89 students and focus the requirements of the students for the effectiveness of online education

2 Net Promoter Score Definition

The first introduction by Fred Reichheld in his 2003 Harvard Business Review article is Net Promoter, which describes practices and reliability in determining customer satisfaction with company products or services (Reichheld, 2003).

Net Promoter Points are indexes from 0 to 10 that measure a customer's intentions in recommending a company's product or service to others, use it as a proxy to assess a customer's overall satisfaction with a company's product or service, and customer loyalty to the brand.

Net promoter scores are a measure of customer a loyalty that measures customers' the customer who scored 9-10 would be the promoter, 7-8 are a passively satisfied customer and 6 below would-be detractors.

For the NPS has been calculated by equation (1) (Enrollment Catalyst and Rick Newberry, 2020) and NPS guide for Figure 2.

Net Promoter Score (NPS) = % Promoters – % Detractors

(1)

Figure 2. NPS guide. (Dinesh & Rajasekaran, 2018)

To test the connection between promoter scores and development, check the scores collected to drive organizations in many organizations. What they find is persuasion. Despite the ways in which the scores themselves migrate by most industry sponsors, net, pioneers of all things consider creating more than double the lead rate. (Dinesh & Rajasekaran, 2018)

3 Result and Discussion

In this study for our group was measuring by google form it is online assessment included 9 questions. As a results aspect of satisfaction for online learning the detailed of result shown in Table1. From the Figure 3. shows the results of the number of courses for students in 1 term. The results show the maximum of 7 subjects represent 25% and the minimum 1 subject is 4% of the total students.

Table 1. Number of courses studied in the semester

Number of course	Number of respondents
1	0
2	3
3	0
4	9
5	24
6	6
7	47

Figure 3. The result number of courses studied in the semester.

The table 2-3 as below shows the different parameters depending on which employees rated the company. The following statements are ranked on the scale 1-5 (where 1 is the least likely). This survey was conducted in Traditional education and online classrooms in which students from one department survey There are 89 students in total.

Table 2. Education structure of students group

Year	Number of respondents
1	27
2	18
3	33
4	11

Table 3. How satisfied are you with teaching in the classroom/ online class room?

Score	Class room (%)	Online classroom(%)
1	0	3.4
2	0	2.2
3	12.4	28.1
4	39.3	37.1
5	48.3	29.2

From Table 3, shown the results of satisfaction with online classroom teaching? It can be seen that most of the students are satisfied with the traditional learning with 48.3% and 29.2% of the online learning styles.

Table 4. Would you like to promote this teaching in the classroom/online course to your friends?

Score	Class room(%)	Online classroom (%)
10-9	45	31.4
8-7	23.6	30.4
6-0	31.4	38.1
NPS	13.6	-6.7

Table 4 is the comparison of the results of traditional learning/ online learning to your friends?. In order to find the NPS score from Table 4, it can be seen that promoters there are 9-10 scoring points, traditional learning accounting for 31.4% and 45% of online learning. And detractors of traditional learning is 31.4% and 38.1% online learning.

Figure 4. The result of type of teaching and learning does student want the most.

4 Conclusion

The calculation of NPS in term traditional learning is 13.6% and minus 6.7% of online learning. Finally the last one of question **“What type of teaching and learning do you want the most?”** the most of student like to study in classroom it was show that 75% (Figure 4.)

Our results indicate that traditional learning has a higher response rate. In addition, both methods have different results in terms of NPS scores for student satisfaction. Due to the general complaints of students about online lessons and the lack of teaching tools and equipment that affect students in traditional learning rather than online learning and how to improve online lessons in the future to reduce the number of teachers. Prospective studies with a larger sample size to assess the effectiveness of tools for assessing student satisfaction to be used as a way to improve online lessons in the future.

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